

A Succinct Review Article on “Problematic Smartphone”

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Abstract:- Problematic smartphone use is proposed by few researchers to be a form of psychological or behavioural addiction on cell phones, closely related to other forms of digital media overuse such as social media dependence or internet addiction disorder. Problematic use can include preoccupation with cell phone communication, excessive money or time spent on cell phones, and use of cell phones in socially or physically inappropriate situations such as driving an automobile. Addicted use can also lead to adverse effects on relationships, mental or physical health, and ensues anxiety if separated from a mobile phone or sufficient signal. Preschool going children and young adults are at highest risk for problematic android phone use. Prevalence of cell phone overuse depends widely on definition and thus the scales used to quantify a subject's behaviors.⁷ In India, addiction is stated at 39-44% for this age group. Depressive symptoms are some of the most serious psychological problems in adolescents; the correlation between depressive symptoms and mobile phone addiction is a critical issue because such symptoms may lead to substance abuse, school failure and even suicide as well.

Key words: Problematic smartphone & Depressive symptoms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Problematic smartphone use is proposed by few researchers to be a form of psychological or behavioural addiction on cell phones, closely related to other forms of digital media overuse such as social media dependence or internet addiction disorder. Other researchers have stated that terminology relating to behavioural addictions in regards to smartphone use can cause additional problems both in research and stigmatization of users, suggesting the term to evolve to problematic smartphone use.¹ Problematic use can include preoccupation with cell phone communication, huge money or time spent on smart phones, and use of cell phones in socially or physically inappropriate situations such as driving an automobile. Increased use can also lead to adverse effects on relationships, mental or physical health, and ensues anxiety if separated from a mobile phone or sufficient signal. Preschool children and young adults are at highest risk for problematic smartphone use.²

The use of smartphone significantly increased since the late 2000s. In 2019 conducts, global smartphone users penetrated in 41.5% of total population. Due to prolific technological advance, the smartphone overuse continued to be a major threat in Asian countries such as China, with around 700 million users are registered in 2018. Digital media overuse is tangentially linked to ocular problems, especially in young age. It has been estimated that 49.8% (4.8 billion) of global population with digital media overuse would be affected with myopia by 2050.³

Identified in current research evidence on the adverse consequences of overusing technology, "mobile phone overuse" has been proposed as a subset of forms of "digital addiction", or "digital dependence", reflecting rose in trends of compulsive behaviour amongst users of technological devices.⁴ Unrestrained use of technological gadgets may affect developmental, social, mental, and physical well-being and result in symptoms akin to various behavioural addictions.⁵ Whilst published research studies have shown associations between digital media use and mental health symptoms or diagnoses, causality has not been established, with nuances and caveats of researchers often perceived wrongly by the general public, or misrepresented by the media.⁶

II. PREVALENCE

Prevalence of mobile phone overuse depends largely on definition and thus the scales used to quantify a subject's behaviors.⁷ In India, addiction is stated at 39-44% for this age group.⁸ Under different diagnostic criteria, the estimated prevalence ranges vary from 0 to 38%, with self-attribution of cell phone addiction exceeding the prevalence estimated in the studies themselves.⁹

III. EFFECTS

Overuse of cell phones may be associated with adverse outcomes on mental and physical health, in addition to having an impact on how users communicate socially.¹⁰

IV. SOCIAL

The presence of smartphones in everyday life may affect social interactions amongst teenagers. Present evidence shows that smartphones are not only decreasing

face-to-face social interactions between teenagers, but are also making the youth less likely to talk to adults.¹¹

V. HEALTH

Findings show that many users associate cell phone usage with headaches, impaired memory and concentration, fatigue, dizziness, and sleep disturbances.¹²

VI. PSYCHOLOGICAL

There is a huge data of research on cell phone use, and its positive and negative influence on the human's psychological mind, mental health, and social interaction. Cell phone users may experience stress, disturbed sleep and manifestation of depression, especially adolescent adults. As per the research done by Professor of psychology at San Diego State University Jean M. Twenge, there is a relation between cell phone overuse and depression. In the wake of android phone being evolved, Twenge and her colleagues stated that there was also a rise seen in depressive symptoms and even suicides among adolescents in 2010.¹³

Depressive manifestations are some of the very serious psychological problems in adolescents; the correlation between depressive symptoms and cell phone addiction is a critical issue because such symptoms may lead to substance abuse, school failure and even suicide as well.¹⁴

VII. LOW SELF-ESTEEM AND ANXIETY

The other psychological symptoms that are caused by phone addiction are self-esteem and anxiety. Today, Social Network Service (SNS) is one of the main streams in the world, therefore it dissolved a lot in daily life too. Studies with teens have repeatedly shown that there is significant correlation between high extroversion, high anxiety, low self-esteem, and cell phone usage. The stronger the young person's cell phone addiction, the more likely that individual is to have high mobile phone call time, receive excessive calls, and receive excessive text messages.¹⁴

VIII. CONCLUSION

Teens are consistently shown that there are significant correlation between high extroversion, high anxiety, low self-esteem, and mobile phone usage. The stronger the young person's cell phone addiction, the more likely that individual is to have high mobile phone call time, receive excessive calls, and receive excessive text messages.

Ethical clearance- This review article is a narrative review article hence it is not essential for an ethical clearance.

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